

Studies on the Fries Rearrangement: Part I.

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Fries and Finck¹ observed that acyl derivatives of phenol, on heating with anhydrous aluminium chloride in inert solvents are smoothly converted by intramolecular migration of the acyl group into isomeric ortho- and/or para-hydroxy ketones.

A good deal of work on this reaction has been carried out with phenolic esters of aliphatic saturated² carboxylic acids but esters of unsaturated higher fatty acids, with the exception of oleic acid³, do not appear to have been attempted. In the latter case³ only resinous product and no definite hydroxyketone was obtained. This reaction has now been extended to the esters of erucic and stearolic acids.

Phenol, ortho-, meta- and para- cresols were condensed with erucic and stearolic acid chlorides and the resultant ester products subjected to the Fries rearrangement under the influence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to form the corresponding isomeric ortho- and/or para-hydroxy ketones. Phenol esters give predominantly orthohydroxyketones and only a very small quantity of *p*-hydroxyketones. But in the case of esters of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresols, only orthohydroxy ketones were isolated and no para migration product was obtained. The *o*-hydroxy ketones were separated from the *p*-hydroxy ketones by steam distillation and characterized through their 2 : 4 dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Chlorides :

(a) *Erucic acid chloride* was obtained by the action of thionyl chloride on erucic acid which was prepared from mustard oil through urea adduct complexes technique⁴. The product was distilled at 220°/3 mm.

(b) *Stearolic acid chloride* : Stearolic acid was prepared from methyl oleate by bromination followed by dehydrobromination with alcoholic potassium hydroxide⁵. The acid was converted into its chloride by the action of thionyl chloride, B.P. 210°/15 mm.

1. K. Fries and G. Finck, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 4271.
2. R. Adams, "Organic Reactions", John Wiley & Sons, Inc. London, 1949, Vol. I, 351.
3. A. B. Sen and V. S. Mishra, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **25**, 393.
4. H. Schlenk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5001.
5. R. L. Shriner, "Organic Syntheses", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., London, 1947, Vol. 27, p. 76.

General Method of Preparation :

(i) *Esters*—To 0.1 mole of an appropriate phenol in a 250 ml. round-bottomed flask, fitted with a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel, was added dropwise 0.11 mole of the acid chloride and the mixture warmed on the water-bath till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas had ceased. After cooling, the mixture was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with sodium hydroxide solution (1%) and finally with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The product was distilled under reduced pressure. The results are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Erucate esters of	B.P.	Mol. Formula	Found %		Required %	
			C	H	C	H
Phenyl	173°/10 mm	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2$	80.8	11.0	81.16	11.1
<i>o</i> -cresyl	182°/ 4 mm	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2$	80.9	10.8	81.3	11.2
<i>m</i> -cresyl	198°/ 7 mm	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2$	81.1	10.9	81.3	11.2
<i>p</i> -cresyl	216°/ 6 mm	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2$	80.5	11.16	81.3	11.2

TABLE II

Stearolate esters of	B.P.	Mol. Formula	Found %		Required %	
			C	H	C	H
Phenyl	168°/4 mm	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_2$	80.7	10.0	80.89	10.1
<i>o</i> -cresyl	178°/1 mm	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$	81.0	10.06	81.08	10.27
<i>m</i> -cresyl	190°/2 mm	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$	80.8	10.1	81.08	10.27
<i>p</i> -cresyl	213°/1 mm	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$	80.7	10.3	81.08	10.27

(ii) *Fries Rearrangements*—Finely ground anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.1 mole) was placed in a 250 ml. round-bottomed flask, equipped with a dropping funnel, a reflux condenser and a CaCl_2 -tube. 0.06 mole of the ester was gradually added and the reaction mixture in the flask was heated to 115°–20° in an oil bath for two hours, during which the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas had subsided. The reddish puffy reaction mass was then cooled and decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with water and dried. After evaporating off the solvent the product was distilled under diminished pressure.

The ortho- and the para-isomers of the hydroxy ketones obtained from the Fries migration of esters were separated from each other by means of steam distillation. The product that distilled with steam was found to conform to Pyman's test⁶, specific for *o*-hydroxyketones. The results are given in Tables III and IV. The low yields of the *o*-hydroxy ketones obtained were due to the formation of high proportion of resinous mass giving no identifiable product.

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6. C. E. Coultehard, J. Marshall and F. L. Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280.

TABLE III
Fries rearrangement of Erucate Esters

Esters	Ketonic products	Yield %	B.P.	Found %		Required %		2 : 4 Dinitro Phenyl Hydrazone			
				C	H	C	H	M.P.	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen Found %	Nitrogen Required %
Phenyl erucate	2'-hydroxy phenyl heneicosen-13, one-1.	27	—	81.0	11.2	81.16	11.1	140°	C ₃₄ H ₅₀ O ₅ N ₄	9.6	9.4
	4'-hydroxy phenyl heneicosen-13, one-1.	7	260°/10 mm.	80.9	10.9	81.16	11.1	167°	C ₃₄ H ₅₀ O ₅ N ₄	9.3	9.4
<i>o</i> -cresyl erucate	2'-hydroxy 3-methyl phenyl heneicosen-13, one-1.	19	225°/3 mm.	81.1	11.4	81.3	11.2	139°	C ₃₅ H ₅₂ O ₅ N ₄	9.1	9.2
<i>m</i> -cresyl erucate	2'-hydroxy 4'-methyl phenyl heneicosen-13, one-1.	33	230°/4 mm.	81.5	11.0	81.3	11.2	130°	C ₃₅ H ₅₂ O ₅ N ₄	9.0	9.2
<i>p</i> -cresyl erucate	2'-hydroxy 5'-methyl phenyl heneicosen-13, one-1.	39	243°/4 mm.	80.8	11.1	81.3	11.2	110°	C ₃₅ H ₅₂ O ₅ N ₄	9.4	9.2

TABLE IV
Fries rearrangement of Stearolate Esters

Esters	Ketonic Products	Yield %	B.P.	Found %		Required %		2 : 4 Dinitro Phenyl Hydrazone			
				C	H	C	H	M.P.	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen Found %	Nitrogen Required %
Phenyl stearolate	2'-hydroxy phenyl heptadecyn-9, one-1.	43	—	80.9	10.2	80.89	10.1	185°	C ₃₀ H ₄₀ O ₅ N ₄	10.1	10.4
	4'-hydroxy phenyl heptadecyn-9, one-1.	4	263°/8 mm.	80.7	10.0	80.89	10.1	225°	C ₃₀ H ₄₀ O ₅ N ₄	10.2	10.4
<i>o</i> -cresyl stearolate	2'-hydroxy 3'-methyl phenyl heptadecyn-9, one-1.	23.4	242°/6 mm.	80.8	10.3	81.08	10.2	205°	C ₃₁ H ₄₂ O ₅ N ₄	9.9	10.2
<i>m</i> -cresyl stearolate	2'-hydroxy 4'-methyl phenyl heptadecyn-9, one-1.	40.5	210°/3 mm.	80.9	10.4	81.08	10.2	295°	C ₃₁ H ₄₂ O ₅ N ₄	10.3	10.2
<i>p</i> -cresyl stearolate	2'-hydroxy 5'-methyl phenyl heptadecyn-9, one-1.	41	220°/3 mm.	81.0	10.1	81.08	10.2	208°	C ₃₁ H ₄₂ O ₅ N ₄	10.5	10.2

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